

Informative Paper

COMPAS_sCO₂

NEW MATERIALS FOR SCO₂ HEAT EXCHANGERS IN NEXT GENERATION CONCENTRATING SOLAR PLANTS: COMPAS_sCO₂ CONTRIBUTION

Second informative paper

INTRODUCTION

As highlighted in the EC Communication 'A Green Deal Industrial Plan for the Net-Zero Age', the EU has the ambition to speed up its industrial transformation and become a leading player in the net-zero industries of the future. The Plan aims at fostering the deployment of a European industrial manufacturing value chain of key sustainable technologies, including solar. Innovation is at the heart of the Plan as breakthrough technologies will have to be developed and brought to market so that current energy systems will be totally reshaped.

Concentrating solar power (CSP) technologies can largely contribute to the sustainable energy transition. The CSP technology Roadmap of the IEA (IEA, 2010) identified a potential for CSP technologies to cover almost 10% of global electricity by 2050 (net of backup fuels). Against this picture, the reality is that CSP growth has been below expectations during the last years for a series of technical, regulatory, financial and administrative barriers. Global capacity at the end of 2022 was less than 7 GW (IRENA, 2023), very far from the 337 GW capacity projected by the IEA for 2030 in the Roadmap. In order for CSP to become a main driver of the green energy technology revolution, a series of breakthroughs have to occur in a relatively short time frame, in order to increase its competitiveness and lead to market deployment. The Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action "COMPASsCO₂" project (November 2020 – October 2024) addresses some of these challenges by looking at material behaviour and lifetime aspects of the particles and the metals being in contact with them, and the validation in a particle/s-CO₂ heat exchanger.

In our first informative paper (COMPASsCO₂, 2023), we addressed one important element in the innovation development path, namely the design of new heat-transfer materials that can withstand high temperatures and are abrasion-resistant. The focus of this second informative paper is on the development of new metal alloys, and the investigation of their properties both as bulk materials and coatings, as well as the interactions with the substrate steel of the heat exchanger tube.

COMPASsCO₂ informative papers intend to disseminate the main project achievements to a wide audience, in order to increase awareness on sustainable energy technologies and highlight the efforts of both research and industry for the transition to a carbon neutral energy mix in Europe, in line with the Net-Zero Industry Act.

STATE-OF-THE-ART

Materials for components exposed to high temperatures must withstand demanding conditions requiring high temperature strength and oxidation resistance. Usually for temperatures up to 600°C austenitic or ferritic steels present sufficient stability, whilst above 700°C Ni-based superalloys are preferred.

In the special case of CSP with solid particle application, which is the focus of the COMPASsCO₂ project, the materials must also perform under erosive conditions due to the continuous contact with heat carrier particles. Up to now, CSP tested components have been: Ni-based alloys; some austenitic steels or ferritic steels. Coatings are often proposed as solution for environments with high erosion issues. Different hardening coatings as carbides are deposited by thermal spray but they increase the costs of the component and in the case of Ni-based superalloys they also have stability issues due to the large thermal expansion coefficient between the carbide coatings and the fluid catalytic cracking matrix.

In the case of COMPASsCO₂ the targeted component is a heat exchanger in which the external wall must stand the degradation from high temperature oxidation-erosion and the internal wall must be stable in highly carburizing atmosphere (s-CO₂ at 700 °C and 250 bar). Thus, new

materials showing high temperature strength, oxidation resistance, erosion resistance and resistance against carburization are required. The protective new materials should show a significantly longer design lifetimes compared to conventional material solutions. The new materials should also be able to achieve higher operation efficiencies in the CSP s-CO₂ Brayton cycle power plants. One line of investigation in COMPASsCO₂ relates to the interaction between the substrate steels and the heat transfer medium, therefore different nickel-based alloys were selected and thoroughly analysed (microstructure, phase composition, chemical stability and ultimately their lifetime estimation) to assess their effective use in such harsh environments under extreme conditions.

COMPAS_sCO₂ CONTRIBUTION

COMPASsCO₂ contribution to the development of new materials that can support next generation CSP power plants using hypercritical fluids has been focusing on the following two main research streams under WP4: 1) External wall investigations, and 2) Internal wall behaviour evaluation. This allowed to assess the main oxidation/corrosion mechanisms and evaluate the degradation profile of the investigated materials for each of the two atmospheres of the heat exchanger: ambient air and CO₂.

The investigations of oxidation and corrosion resistance were carried out in a test programme shared between FZJ, CIEMAT and CVR. Four commercial alloys which are commonly used in reheater and superheater tubes of power plants given their exceptional properties were analysed (Table 1).

Table 1: Chemical composition (wt.%) of investigated state-of-the-art materials (source: COMPASsCO₂ D4.1, September 2023)

Alloy	Fe	Ni	Co	Cr	Al	Mo	Ti	Mn	Si	C	Other
Sanicro 25	41.5	24.2	1.50	23.4	0.03	0.23	0.03	0.56	0.19	0.084	Cu 2.93, Nb 0.5 W3.47, N 0.28
Alloy 617	1.03	51.9	11.9	22.1	1.16	9.0	0.39	0.09	0.32	0.076	W 0.32
IN740	0.15	48.0	21.4	25.2	1.35	0.53	1.49	0.30	0.18	0.048	Nb 1.5, Ce 0.12
Haynes 282	0.61	52.5	10.1	18.6	1.50	8.7	2.15	0.05	0.25	0.070	Ce 0.17

Erosion testing simulating real conditions behaviour in the HEX was performed at FZJ facilities. The impact of granulated particles (sintered bauxite provided by Saint Gobain) on specimens manufactured for the test was assessed in terms of mass change, metallographic cross-sections (SEM¹, EDX) and optical metallography. The testing was done at different temperatures (600, 700 and 900°C) for 250 hours. Figure 1 presents the results of erosion testing at 900°C in air for IN740, both in terms of cyclic oxidation and oxidation-erosion. The Chromium scale is getting thinner because the surface is being eroded. The images indicate that chromia and titania-rich oxide layers are typically formed, creating a hard barrier on the surface of the material substrate that may enhance corrosion resistance.

¹ Scanning Electron Microscopy and Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy.

Figure 1 : Back scattered electron images of cross-sectioned IN@ 740 (source: COMPASsCO₂ 2nd Stakeholders workshop, September 2023)

Figure 2 shows the mass changes obtained during isothermal exposure in the thermobalance. Mass changes are related to total specimen area, including the sides not exposed to erosion. The data reveal that the oxidation for all investigated alloys obeyed a parabolic rate law for the examined time range up to 72 hours at 900°C. In both tests gases mass changes increased in the order of: Sanicro® 25 < Inconel® 617 < Inconel® 740 < Haynes® 282. The oxidation rates were found to be increased for the alloys when exposed in CO₂, and the effect appeared to be independent of the material. For Haynes® 282 the effect is comparatively the weakest.

Figure 2 : Relative weight changes of Haynes® 282, IN®740, IN®617, and Sanicro® 25 during isothermal oxidation exposure in air (left), and in CO₂ (right) for 72 hours at 900°C (source: FZJ, COMPASsCO₂ 2nd Stakeholders workshop, 25 September 2023)

Cyclic oxidation testing in air and CO₂ at 900°C showed that the mass change data after short durations are in agreement with the mass changes obtained during isothermal oxidation. Haynes® 282 shows the highest mass gains, Sanicro® 25 the lowest, IN® 740 and IN® 617 exhibit intermediate values. After longer exposure, Sanicro® 25 exhibits a decrease in mass. The effect seems to be stronger in CO₂ when compared to air. IN® 617 started to exhibit slightly decreasing mass changes at about 2500 hours in CO₂. Under these test conditions, the decreasing mass change is typically related to oxide scale spallation.

A greater oxide spallation was observed for Sanicro® 25, which has a higher coefficient of thermal expansion, as compared to the other Ni-based alloys. One possible explanation is that the difference in the oxide microstructures plays a role. The fast-growing scales containing defects (vacancies, pores) on IN® 740 and Haynes® 282 are likely to have a lower modulus of elasticity resulting in less stress generation upon the same thermal mismatch strain induced

between the oxide and metal upon cooling. Another possible explanation for better scale adherence on Haynes 282 and IN® 740 is the presence of minor Cerium additions in their analysed compositions, which enhances oxidation resistance. It is noteworthy that IN® 617, without a reactive element addition, showed slight weight losses at the end of 3000 hours exposure in the CO₂ atmosphere, possibly indicating initial spallation.

Figure 3 : Relative weight change of Haynes® 282, IN®740, IN®617, and Sanicro® 25 during cyclic oxidation exposure in air (left), and in CO₂ (4.5) (right) for 3000 hours at 900°C. (source: FZJ, COMPASSCO₂ 2nd Stakeholders workshop, 25 September 2023)

No substantial differences in the oxide scale growth rates were found between exposures in air and CO₂ under the tested conditions (at atmospheric pressure). Moreover, no indications for internal carburization were seen from the SEM cross-sectional analysis. At the same time internal nitride formation was observed in the cross-sections meaning that the oxide scales on the Ni-based alloys were permeable to nitrogen. This observation indicates that the oxide scale growth occurs by a mechanism not involving access of CO₂ molecules to the oxide/metal interface.

Long-term thermal oxidation tests have been conducted by CIEMAT in tubular furnaces with closed quartz tubes at high temperatures (700 and 900 °C) with a CO₂ atmosphere and constant controlled flow of CO₂ gas.

Weight gain measurements of the materials tested at 700°C under two qualities of CO₂ (industrial and research grades) were measured every 500 h up to 5000 hours, and the results are shown in Figure 3. Under each CO₂ quality, there is a clear difference between the materials tested. Haynes® 282 weight gains are higher than the rest of materials, followed by Inconel® 617 and 740 with similar trend between them, and Sanicro® 25 presents the lowest value. These results on weight gain could be associated with the titanium content (Table 1) following the trend: Haynes®282>Inconel®740≥Inconel®617> Sanicro® 25.

Figure 4 : Weight gain measurements at 700 °C for Sanicro® 25, Inconel® 740, Inconel® 617B and Haynes® 282 under CO₂ atmosphere: a) IG and b) RG (source: COMPASsCO₂ D4.1)

All the materials showed an increase in the thickness of the oxide scales with increasing exposure time in agreement to weight gain measurements. Comparing the different materials, the thicker oxide layer after 5000 h of exposure time² corresponds to Haynes® 282, followed by Inconel® 617 and Inconel® 740, and Sanicro® 25 with the thinner oxide layer.

Internal oxidation zones were detected below the oxide layer in the specimens of Ni-base alloys. The internal oxidation increases with increasing the alloy Al content.

The weight gain evolution with long-term exposures shows that the corrosion kinetic follows a parabolic law in all the materials tested, as it was expected for the alloys forming protective oxide scales. No significant differences were observed comparing the results of the two grades of commercial CO₂. This result is relevant for the design of the system and can play an important role in the cost of the operation of the power plant. In addition, the results obtained in the tests of the different laboratories are also comparable between them.

EDS mapping of the materials tested at 700 °C during 5000 h showed that the scale in the inner part contains mainly Cr and Mn oxides. Underneath the oxide layer there is a depletion of Cr in all materials. An internal oxidation zone was detected below the oxide layer in the specimens of Ni-base alloys. This internal oxidation of Inconel® 617 is detected by the presence of oxygen and aluminium while the titanium can be observed as islands of

² In the case of specimens tested at 1000, 3000 and 5000h a nickel layer was deposited over oxide layer in order to protect them.

precipitates. On the contrary, the internal oxidation of Inconel® 740 and Haynes® 282 is correlated with aluminium and titanium. In both materials, the titanium is also present in the outer oxide layer. The thickness of the oxide and the internal oxidation is greater for Haynes® 282 and Inconel® 740, according to the titanium content of the alloy.

X-ray photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to study the evolution of the composition of the oxide layer in the studied materials after 500 h and 5000 h of exposure time at 700 °C under IG and RG CO₂ qualities with no significant differences observed for the two CO₂ grades. The depth profile of the oxide layer is in accordance with EDS observations. The oxide layers are mainly composed of Cr in all the materials and an outer thin oxide with Ti and/or Mn depending on the concentration of these alloying elements in each material. Furthermore, Al was also detected after long exposures in the case of Ni-base materials.

Table 2 summarizes the thickness of the oxide scales obtained by SEM-EDS and XPS spectroscopy. The XPS thickness is determined as the point in which oxygen concentration reduces to 50 % of the oxygen concentration at the plateau. Similar values were obtained in both techniques and the growth oxide layer with time is in accordance with the increase of thickness with the Ti content of the alloy, as concluded for the weight gain measurements.

Table 2: Oxide layer thickness of specimens tested at 700 °C (source: COMPASsCO₂ D4.1, September 2023)

MATERIAL	700 °C, time	Thickness SEM (µm)	Thickness XPS (µm)
Sanicro 25	500 h	0.6	0.5
Inconel 617B		1.3	1.5
Inconel 740		0.7	0.7
Haynes 282		1.8	2.1
Sanicro 25	1000 h	0.6	
Inconel 617B		1.3	
Inconel 740		0.7	
Haynes 282		2.1	
Sanicro 25	3000 h	1.1	
Inconel 617B		2.3	
Inconel 740		2.7	
Haynes 282		3.0	
Sanicro 25	5000 h	1.4	0.7
Inconel 617B		2.5	1.8
Inconel 740		2.4	2.7
Haynes 282		4.8	2.8

In order to assess the temperature influence on the material performance, an additional testing was conducted on industrial grade CO₂ atmosphere at 900°C. In the case of Ni-based alloys the weight gains are one order of magnitude greater than specimens tested at 700°C. At 900°C, Haynes 282 also shows higher values than Inconel alloys with similar values between them. In the case of the Sanicro® 25, the material behavior is clearly different due to a decrease of weight gains after 500 hours testing, even with negative values. Such a behavior can be associated with formation of poorly adherent oxide scales prone to spallation from the metal upon cooling.

The SEM images of the oxide layers of the materials after 500 and 1000 h exposure at 900°C indicate that the oxide scales are significantly thicker than those formed at the lower temperature, even in the case of Sanicro® 25, as expected and in agreement with the weight gain measurements.

DISCUSSION WITH STAKEHOLDERS

In order to present and validate the research findings and discuss main open issues an expert workshop was organised on September 25th, 2023 back-to-back with the international conference on High temperature corrosion and oxidation in Marktheidenfeld (Germany). The workshop was organized around two main sessions, the first dealing with advanced materials for abrasive environments and the second one focusing on material behaviour in sCO₂ environments. Representatives from the COMPASsCO₂ consortium had the opportunity to interact with experts from industry and academia to further advance on the work. In particular, research conducted in other countries (US) and industrial experiences with the development of special metals were presented and related to COMPASs CO₂ findings. Main recommendations received from stakeholders helped further refine the research and elaborate the deliverables.

NEXT STEPS AND CONCLUSIONS

Under WP4, a series of analyses to determine materials' resistance and durability have been conducted. Four Nickel-based superalloys have been selected for their exceptional properties that make them already suitable in several industrial applications: Sanicro® 25, Inconel®617, Inconel® 740 and Haynes®282. Erosion, cyclic oxidation and long-term oxidation testing was conducted, and some main considerations can be drawn.

Firstly, the erosion rate seems to be strictly dependent on temperature, as degradation was observed mostly at 900°C. The most prone to erosion was Haynes® 282 while the lowest mass loss was observed for Sanicro® 25 and Inconel® 617. Less erosion showed less granulate deposition and could not be attributed to mechanical properties, meaning that the oxide scale determines the erosion properties.

The oxidation for all investigated alloys obeys a parabolic rate law for the examined time range up to 72 hours at 900°C. The same ranking of mass change was observed in both test gases, although slightly higher oxidation rates were detected in CO₂ environment. Haynes® 282 showed the highest mass change. Cyclic oxidation testing confirms the results of thermogravimetry experiments. Sanicro® 25 had more extensive scale spallation which is not in agreement with the low scale growth rate. Slightly higher tendency to scale spallation was observed in CO₂ compared to industrial air. Scanning Electron Microscopy indicates that nickel-based alloys have substantial amount of internal oxidation, which increases with increasing aluminium content. Titanium effect on thickness was observed and further analysed as it is known to cause p-type doping effect, substituting for chromium.

Finally, long-term erosion testing was conducted to assess the influence of temperature (700 vs. 900°C) and the quality of CO₂ gas used (research vs. industrial grade). Weight gain measurements of the materials tested at 700°C under both industrial and research-grade CO₂ were measured every 500 h up to 5000 hours. For each CO₂ quality, there is a clear difference among the materials, with Haynes® 282 showing the highest weight gains. Weight gain could be associated with titanium content. All materials showed an increase in the thickness of the oxide scales with increasing exposure time in agreement with weight gain measurements. The thicker oxide layer after 5000 h of exposure time corresponds to Haynes® 282.

During the next project stages, high-pressure sCO₂ tests at simulated operating conditions will be performed. To this end, a Supercritical Carbon dioxide Autoclave (ScCAc) system was assembled at CVR. Corrosion tests in flowing supercritical CO₂ at high temperature will be carried out on specially prepared material samples. Corrosion testing parameters will set to: 700°C; 120 bar; industrial grade CO₂ (99.995). Expected testing duration will be 1000h for novel material and 3000h for state-of-the-art. Results will be disseminated in project

deliverables, scientific papers, as well as the final conference. A communication-oriented paper will also be prepared to inform non-expert audience.

The project COMPASsCO₂ opens the path for a future commercial application of solar s-CO₂ Brayton cycle with the development of novel materials and components specifically designed for the linkage of the solar/storage system with power cycle via a particles / s-CO₂ heat exchanger. This requires the joint research effort of CSP and material researchers as well and industrial components manufacturer specialists.

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ABOUT COMPAS_sCO₂

COMPAS_sCO₂ aims to integrate CSP particle systems into highly efficient s-CO₂ Brayton power cycles for electricity production. Its research focus is on three main technological improvements:

- **development of new particles**

In order for particles to meet high temperatures new ceramic particles with improved performance will be developed and tested under relevant conditions

- **development of new metal alloys**

Answers about how the processing and combination with substrate steels will affect the microstructure, phase composition and also chemical stability of the newly developed materials will be provided. Modelling the degradation progress over time to estimate the lifetime of the new materials and coatings under different conditions will be performed.

- **development of the heat exchanger section**

To validate the interaction between the developed particles and the new structural materials in a relevant environment, the project includes the design, construction and testing of a heat exchanger section. Parameters relevant for the lifetime, like attrition rates, and performance parameters, like heat transfer, on the tube and first operating experiences are generated in a relevant heat exchanger environment.

In addition to the research component, COMPAS_sCO₂ includes a **communication and dissemination package for a wide range of stakeholders**. This Horizon 2020 project has a four-year duration (2020-2024) and is coordinated by DLR, with 12 European partners.

For more information

Check the project's website: www.compassco2.eu

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